

CONCEPT, CONTENT AND ESSENCE OF MEDIA LITERACY

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Abstract: This article describes the concept, content and essence of media literacy. At the same time, information is provided about the necessity and importance of media literacy in society.

Key words: media literacy, media education, media text, information, mass media, media education.

There are different opinions about the concept of media literacy, and according to the American International Encyclopedia of Society, it is noted that "media literacy" means being active and literate while feeling the responsibility as a citizen in society, being able to receive and create media texts, it means to be able to analyze and evaluate, to be able to understand the socio-cultural and political content of modern media.

According to S. Firestone, professor of the Royal University of London, media literacy is a movement whose main task is to encourage people to understand, create and evaluate the cultural significance of audiovisual and printed texts.

In our opinion, media literacy is a critical view of all the information transmitted through mass media, an unbiased approach to them, and a conscious approach to sorting each transmitted information.

The goal of media literacy is to understand the priorities and shortcomings of each media, to be able to sort out the information distributed by them and to form the skills to accept the necessary, while the main task is to limit it, realizing the manipulative power of any information consumed by people. It is also to help people understand the role of media and citizen journalism.

The media is a powerful force in the lives of young people. Music, television, video games, magazines, and other media have a powerful influence on how we see the world, often beginning in childhood. In order for consumers to be able to critically analyze media, they need to develop media literacy skills and habits from childhood. These skills include accessing media at a basic level, analyzing it critically based on specific concepts, evaluating it based on that analysis, and finally producing the media itself. This process of learning media literacy skills is called media education.

The promotion of media education in the 21st century was recognized by

UNESCO as a priority direction of cultural and educational development, and it was emphasized that media literacy can be increased in this way. UNESCO supports the development of media and media literacy to improve people's critical thinking and good decision-making. The organization is particularly committed to building the capacity of politicians, educators, media professionals, youth organizations and vulnerable populations in this field, and assists member states in formulating national media and information literacy policies and strategies.

The oldest organization that studies media literacy is the National Telemedia Council, based in Madison, Wisconsin, and led by Mariel Rowe for more than 50 years. The organization initially published a media literacy magazine known as "Telemedium". Today, media literacy is widely promoted and promoted in countries around the world.

Media literacy is the study of media, which is based on the following results of media education and aims to:

- understanding the impact of media on individuals and society;
- understanding of mass communication process;
- ability to understand and analyze media texts;
- understanding the media context;
- creation of media texts and their analysis;
- sets the tasks of evaluating media texts and sorting them.

Today, the media, i.e., mass media, cinema, theater, types of art, cultural exchanges, any information transmitted through the Internet has a certain effect on the human mind and changes its worldview. is causing change. The main purpose of the application of the above-mentioned concepts and the pursuit of media education, media literacy, media criticism and media studies today is the creation of information, understanding the process of its dissemination, commercial, political, economic, spiritual and cultural purposes. is to be able to evaluate the information being disseminated while understanding its essence.

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